

USE OF DIFFERENT TEACHING METHODS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8037335>

Annotation:

Nowadays technology, information and knowledge explosion have led to the increase of teaching and learning English as an international language. Teaching and learning English in different countries have been faced with some problems. English has been taught in schools in Uzbekistan since some years ago. The organizing the learning method is to meet a specific educational goal. Programmed teaching, lectures, and practical display are considered as examples of teaching methods.

Key words:

students ,teachers different levels of education, educational medium, effective and desirable teaching, human activities, learning , second language, educators

Аннотация:

В настоящее время технологии, информация и взрыв знаний привели к увеличению преподавания и изучения английского языка как международного языка. Преподавание и изучение английского языка в разных странах столкнулись с некоторыми проблемами. Английский язык преподается в школах Узбекистана несколько лет назад. Организация метода обучения заключается в достижении конкретной образовательной цели. В качестве примеров методов обучения рассматриваются программированное обучение, лекции и практический показ.

Ключевые слова:

студенты, учителя разных уровней образования, образовательная среда, эффективное и желаемое обучение, деятельность человека, обучение, второй язык, педагоги

Annotatsiya:

Hozirgi kunda texnologiya, axborot va bilimlarning portlashi ingliz tilini xalqaro til sifatida o'qitish va o'rganishni oshirishga olib keldi. Turli mamlakatlarda ingliz tilini o'rgatish va o'rganish ba'zi qiyinchiliklarga duch keldi. O'zbekiston maktablarida bir necha yil avval ingliz tili o'qitilib kelinmoqda. O'qitish usulini tashkil etish - bu aniq ta'lim maqsadiga erishish. Dasturlashtirilgan o'qitish, ma'ruzalar va amaliy ko'rgazmalar o'qitish usullariga misol sifatida qaraladi.

Kalit so'zlar:

talabalar, ta'limning turli darajadagi o'qituvchilari, ta'lim muhiti, samarali va kerakli ta'lim, inson faoliyati, o'rganish, ikkinchi til, o'qituvchilar

Nowadays, with the advancement of science and technology, English is essential as an international language. So in this new millennium, language is the guiding factor for trading, politics, economy, science and technology. Extending the English learning is a prerequisite due to the growing development in the field of science and technology and the need to become aware of them through the mass media. This will be achieved by the development of English language teaching in a principle manner. And second language teachers need special training to learn how to teach the language.

Teaching method is different from the concept of “educational medium” (a means of exposing the students to a data source, such as text books, TV, PC, or the teacher and other students). In fact several different teaching methods may be used in an educational medium (such as programmed teaching, lectures, and practical display on TV) or a specific teaching method in several different educational mediums (Such as the use of programmed teaching in text books or TV). Teaching method is a set of procedures and experimental activities performed to achieve a certain goal. The best method is the one which spends the least time and with there sources available, and thus achieves the highest returns. Teaching method is a set of activities that are carried out according to the conditions and possibilities to provide the most favorable area for the effective and desirable teaching. Learning is any constant change in behavior which comes from the experience. It must be considered that teaching does not mean learning and any teaching necessarily lead to learning. All over the world, educational institutions implementing new ideas, methods, and technology based innovations to enhance the students’ knowledge in the sphere of English. Basically, teaching must include two major components sending and receiving information. Ultimately, a teacher tries his best to impart knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower people, strengthen governance. The biggest challenge any teacher faces is capturing the students’ attention, and putting across ideas in such a way that it stays with them long after they have left the classroom. For this to happen, classroom experience should be redefined and innovative ideas that make teaching learning methods more effective should be implemented.

The present decade and the past century are different from what is known to the history. Very deep and broad changes which have never been seen in the past have affected all human activities and teaching is no more based on the transfer of constant information to passive students. Minds filled with Inflexible material cannot figure out the present and future complexity and dynamic.

Teaching and learning English as a second language has long been of interest for teachers and educators. Everyone has tried to reduce the obstacles and difficulties in learning English. But unfortunately, few people are able to reduce these problems. Many students and teachers of English Language have always encountered with problems that did not made the full learning of this language. As effects and evidence show, our students have difficulty in learning English at different levels of education and always complain about its unclearness. Basically the problem occurs when we do not learn the basic principles of something. This issue may happen in everything and when we refer to its origin we see that all the problems can be resolved. Teaching English in different countries have faced with many problems although most teachers and students spent many hours in classrooms to teach and learn the language, they have not had success in this area.

Despite a great experience, most teachers still have not really found what is important in language teaching and learning in the classroom they usually ignore the most important element of any training session that includes providing a valuable learning experience which has a significant contribution in the development of second language performance. It should be noted that teachers teach a set of individuals and any teaching process must enrich the emotions of both student and teacher. If language is taken from the human society, human civilization will be destroyed, thus teaching and learning language is a priority in the field of education.

References:

1. Eaglestone R. (2000). *Doing English*. Great Britain Routledge.
2. Jarvis S. (2002). Topic continuity in L2 English article use. *Studies in second language Acquisition*, 24.
3. Carter R. (2002). *Teaching English to speakers of other languages*. CUP.
4. Cooper, L. Robert, Joshua A. Fishman. "A Study of Language Attitudes." In J.A. Fishman, R.L. Cooper, Conrad A.W. *The Spread of English*.
5. Crystal, D. *English as a Global Language*. 2nd edition. New York: CUP, 2013.
6. Richard J. "Conversational Competence through Role Play Activities", *RELC Journal* 16 (1), 1985, p. 82-100.
7. Richards, J.C., Rodgers T.S. *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001. P. 236.